

MICROBIOCENOSIS OF THE ORAL CAVITY IN INFLAMMATORY PERIODONTAL DISEASES

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Purpose of the study. To conduct a comparative assessment of the effectiveness of classical and molecular genetic methods for diagnosing inflammatory periodontal diseases.

Material and methods. During a microbiological study, we studied the composition of the microflora of the periodontal sulcus in 61 patients. We collected samples from the periodontal sulcus using sterile disks after a 2-minute contact exposure, then they were placed in test tubes with 1 ml of sugar broth, 0.1 ml of which was sown on nutrient environment. Within 24 hours after incubation in a thermostat ($t=37^{\circ}\text{C}$), the number of grown colonies on the plate was counted and recalculated per 1 cm² area. When studying microbiocenosis, standard nutrient media were used: – blood agar – to calculate the total microbial contamination; – yolk-salt agar – for staphylococci; – sugar broth – for streptococci; – vegetable-milk medium – for lactobacilli; – Sabouraud's medium – for yeast-like fungi of the genus *Candida*. To identify obligate anaerobic microorganisms of the oral cavity, in parallel with classical bacteriological methods, the real-time polymerase chain reaction (PCR) method was used.

Result. Analysis of data obtained using microbiological methods depending on severity allowed us to distribute clinical groups into subgroups: Group I – (15 patients with mild severity). In the clinical subgroups of persons diagnosed with mild periodontal disease, the analysis identified 1-2-3 component associations in 46.6%; 33.3%; 20%. 46.6% of patients (7) had *P. gingivalis* monoinfection; in 33.3% (5) associations of two species were determined: *Treponema denticola* + *B. forsythus*, in 3 in 20% of cases - associations of three species: *P. gingivalis* + *Treponema denticola* + *B. forsythus*. Group II - 22 (36%). When analyzing the structure of markers isolated from samples of dental plaque in patients with moderate severity of the disease, it was found that *P. gingivalis* markers were identified most often (26.3%), in 13.8% of cases - *B. forsythus* and *T. denticola*. Microorganisms in 57.1% of cases were mainly represented by associations of three species, in 14.3% by associations of two, and in 28.6% by associations of four species. Group III - 24

(39.3%). In clinical subgroups with severe disease from the oral mucosa, 1-2 component associations were identified in 21.3%, 2-3 and 3-4 components - 46.1% of cases, 4-5 components in 32.6% of cases . The increasing complexity of microbial associations found in the gingival margin has contributed to the progression and aggravation of chronic periodontal diseases.

Conclusions. Against the background of a chronic inflammatory process, favorable conditions are created for the development of pathogenic microflora, which in turn leads to the support of inflammatory processes in periodontal tissues. The results of microbiological studies give reason to believe that when treating periodontal tissue diseases in patients with different severity of the disease, one should take into account not only the severity of the disease, but also the species composition of the microflora. This approach is appropriate and rational in the selection of antibacterial drugs in complex treatment, having previously determined the sensitivity of the oral microflora to them.

Literature Review:

1. Periodontal Disease in Adolescents
2. Papapanou, P. N. (1996). "Periodontal diseases in the 21st century: A global perspective." *Journal of Periodontology*, 67(1), 22-30.
3. This foundational paper discusses the prevalence of periodontal diseases in adolescents, highlighting risk factors and the importance of early diagnosis.
4. Microbiological Factors in Gingivitis
5. Hajishengallis, G., & Darveau, R. P. (2012). "Periodontitis: A systemic disease that impacts overall health." *Journal of Periodontal Research*, 47(4), 517-526.
6. This study explores the microbial communities associated with periodontal diseases, emphasizing the role of specific bacteria in disease onset.
7. Immune Response to Oral Pathogens
8. Van Dyke, T. E., & Serhan, C. N. (2003). "Resolution of inflammation: A new paradigm for the pathogenesis of periodontal disease." *Journal of Periodontology*, 74(2), 334-344.
9. This article discusses the innate and adaptive immune responses in periodontal disease, focusing on the cytokine profiles associated with inflammation.
10. Hormonal Changes and Oral Health
11. Kauffman, M. A., & Kauffman, J. A. (2000). "Hormonal changes and the periodontal disease relationship." *Dental Clinics of North America*, 44(3), 611-628.

12. This review examines the effects of hormonal changes during puberty on periodontal health, including increased susceptibility to gingival inflammation.